

Formulation And Evaluation of Herbal Face Gel by Using *Azadirachta Indica* Extract

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ABSTRACT

Our main aim is to formulate and evaluate herbal face gel by using extracts of *Azadirachta indica* leaves. The herbal remedies are superior to the synthetic remedy in terms of effectiveness. In comparison to conventional cosmetics, Indian medicinal plants have a greater variety of pharmacological activity, safer to the body and is easier to obtain. Several type of herbs like Alovera,Neem,Turmaric,Sandalwood,Cucumber,Rose.They exhibit a range of qualities, including those are antiseptic, antiacne,anti-aging,anti-wrinkle, antioxidant & antimicrobial activity . Methods: The extraction of neem leaf is done by maceration method using ethanol. By standard procedure four formulations were formulated using Carbopol and Methyl cellulose polymers in definite proportions, the formulation is evaluated for various evaluation parameters like pH, Spreadability, Viscosity, Drug Content, Diffusion study, Etc. Result: We have prepared four formulations; NCF,NCD,NMF & NMD by using Carbapol 940 &Methyl cellulose polymers.The prepared formulations exhibit acceptable pH, spreadability, viscosity and homogeneity. In NCF,NCD,NMF & NMD formulations the NCF formulation shows better results compared to NCD,NMF & NMD. Conclusion: Hence it was concluded that NCF formulation has suitable concentration than NCD,NMF,NMD formulations, for exhibiting excellent anti-acne activity. The evaluation test also indicated that the formulation has acceptable pH, spreadability, viscosity, and stability.

Keywords: *Azadirachta indica*, Anti-acne activity, Neem leaf extract, Carbopol 940 & Methyl Cellulose..

INTRODUCTION

DEFINITION (1, 2)

The skin is biggest organ of body. It is soft and help to movement. It also prevent breaking by its tough nature. The skin smoothness and thickness changes from area to area of the body.

Functions of the skin (3, 5)

- **Protection:** It act as physical protector against infective agent, water loss, UV light, mechanical damage and other external environment.
- **Sensation:** Skin is largest sensory organ of the body. It gives sense against the pain, temperature, touch, etc.

- **Mobility:** it help for movement.
- **Endocrine activity:** it help calcium absorption by producing Vitamin D and it is endocrine process.
- **Exocrine activity:** Skin secretes the many liquids like water, urea, Ammonia. Sebum, sweat, and pheromones by their respective glands.
- **Immunity:** Secret the cytokine a bioactive substance.
- **Regulation of Temperature:** By regulating water movement through skin it maintains temperature of the body and haemostat.

SKIN LAYERS (4,6)

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Epidermis:

Epidermis is contains Epithelial cell. It contains both live and dead cells. The older cells are pushed forward by the younger cells at the bottom of the epidermis, fastly divide. The epidermis is not directly got nutrients because no direct vessel. The dermis is supply the nourishment and nutrients to epidermis. Which allows the required molecules to diffuse here. Desmosomes form a very tight connection between epidermal cells.

Cell types that exist in the epidermis are:

Keratinocytes: These are the important cells and (5% of cells).

Melanocytes are basal layer and they are called as pigment cells and produce pigment.

Langerhans cells are present in mid dermis, Merkel cells. Langerhan cells helps immunological cells.

Epidermis consists of five layers, namely from inside to outside;

1. Stratum germinativum
2. Stratum spinosum
3. Stratum granulosum
4. Stratum lucidum
5. Stratum corneum.

Dermis

Below the epidermis layer is called as dermis and which contains two dense network

1. Dense network of fibers which help for stretch skin.
2. Dense network of collagen for provide strength to skin.

Dermis have the arteries, nerves, lymphatic cells, sweat glands, elastin fibers. It also contains salt, interfibrillar gel of glycosaminoglycan, water.

Arteries supplies nutrients to both epidermis and dermis layer. Nerves provide pressure and pain

feeling. Lymphatic cells defense system. Sweat glands regulates the temperature by releasing sweat. Cell types found in dermis are:

Fibroblasts: produce collagen

Macrophages: scavenger cells

Mast cells: these are immunological cells by interacting eosinophills.

Hypodermis:

It is the last layer of skin and deeper most layer. The glands like sweat, sebaceous are originated from these layer and hair follicle also developed from here. The muscles and bones are directly connected to hypodermis layer.

Sweat gland- Release thin salt solution and that regulates the temperatures of body and skin by evaporates of the solution and cools the skin. The body contains sweat glands everywhere. The amount of sweat develops varies and it depends on the temperature produce and the level of heat generated by skeletal muscle activity, and a variety of emotional aspects.

Sebaceous Gland- Sebaceous gland are present in hair follicle. It develops Sebum and it is an oily product that is released from hair follicles onto the skin.

Routes of Drug Permeation Through Skin

Three primary routes of skin absorption

1) Primary Transcellular: The molecules are passed through certain packed coenocytes into and out of cell membrane.

2) Secondary Intercellular: The chemicals are passed around coenocytes in the lipid rich extracellular region.

3) Thirdly Transappendageal: These transports are helped by glands of skin.

COMMON SKIN PROBLEMS (7, 8)

Some common skin problems include:

Dermatitis – skin inflammation due to many stimuli.

Fungal infections – causes tinea. It is also called as athlete foot.

Skin cancer – long term expose to ultra-violet rays.

Sunburn – burning of skin due sun rays

Warts – Caused by a virus.

ACNE (9, 10, 11)

Acne vulgaris is a most common disorder of the skin. It occurs almost all individuals in life. The acne happens mainly at teenage age. But substantial numbers of men and women between 20-30 years of age are also affected by the disorder.

➤ Acne may be classified as

- Comedonal- In this type of acne inflammation is not happens. It is non inflammatory acne.

It is divided into 2 types

Whiteheads- it is white colored, fresh acne and raised bumps. It is also called as closed comedo.

Blackhead- it is also called open comedo. In these acne pores are open, dark colored skin roughage, it consist of melanin, sebum and follicular cells.

- Papules are less than 5mm in size. They appear in red in Colour and solid in nature.
- Pustules are circumscribed skin elevations containing purulent material.
- Cysts and nodules both are solid, elevated lesions involving deeper dermal and subcutaneous tissue. Cysts are less than 5mm in diameter whereas nodules more than 5mm.

TOPICAL DRUG DELIVERY SYSTEM(12, 13, 14)

The route of drug administration decide the result of disease treatment. The topical drugs are administered mainly through the skin. Topical drug delivery system is defined as the method to administered of formulation

to the skin to treat cutaneous disorders or the cutaneous manifestations of a general disease.

- External topical drug delivery system is the drug delivery system in which drug is applied to the cutaneous tissues by spreading, spraying, or other means in order to cover the affected area.
- Internal topical drug delivery system is used to treat local action and in this system drug is supplied through the mucosal membrane like orally, vaginally, or on anorectal tissues.

Advantages of Topical Drug Delivery System:

- Pass the first pass metabolism.
- When allergic reaction or eradication happens then easily terminated.
- Large surface area to administered drug.
- Increase the physiological and pharmacological response.
- Patient compliance is good.

Disadvantages of Topical Drug Delivery System:

- Skin irritation chances are more.
- Some drug are poorly absorb due less permeability.

HERBAL COSMETICS (15, 16, 17)

Herbal cosmetics is also called as natural cosmetics. Since the dawn of civilization, the people have been used for cosmetic purpose on others by their appearance. The variety of herbal cosmetic formulations are available like creams , shampoo, gels, paste, soaps, face powder, etc. The most of herbal cosmetics contents natural ingredients so that reason the negative effect is less or not side effect, the natural ingredients gives nutrients and useful minerals. Many plants like Kesar, Ashwagandha, Chandan, Neem, Aleovera and many others are used in herbal cosmetics. Plant parts or extract of plant parts are used for cosmetic purposes.

Herbal cosmetics are maintained in effective manner with following benefits

- Harmful effect is less or no because of available natural ingredients.
- Present from ancient time.
- Easily available.
- Along with this many advantages are present.

HERBAL GELS (18, 19, 20, 21)

Herbal gel are topical gels which contains herbal drugs. It is a semi solid, jelly-like product, in that solid material is dispersed in liquid vehicle and it ranging from soft and weak to hard and tough preparation. It is used as protectants, antiseptics, and antimicrobials.

Benefits of herbal gel:

- **Skin Protection:** Herbal gels can protect the skin from environmental factors.
- **Wound Healing:** Herbal gels can speed up the healing process.
- **Anti-inflammatory:** Herbal gels can help with inflammation.
- **Moisturizing:** Herbal gels can moisturize the skin.
- **Soothing:** Herbal gels can soothe the skin
- **Compatible with sensitive skin:** Herbal gels can be compatible with sensitive skin
- **No side effects:** Herbal gels can be free of side effects

Preparation and Evaluation Properties of gels.

Gels are prepared by electing proper excipients like vehicles, gelling agents and additives. Gels are formulated by thermal, flocculation or chemical methods. The prepared gels are tested like homogeneity, pH, drug content, viscosity,

spreadability, extrudability, skin irritation and in vitro diffusion studies.

PLANT PROFILE(22, 23, 24)

- **Common Name:** Neem
- **Botanical Name:** *Azadirachta indica*
- **Biological Source:** Neem consists of the fresh or dried leaves and seed oil of *Azadirachta indica*. It is cultivated mainly in the tropical and semi tropical area as a wild plant. It is commonly available below 3500m altitude. The tree is from India, Nepal, Bangladesh and Pakistan also found in Malaysia and China.

Fig No. 5: Leaves of *Azadirachta indica*

- **Kingdom:** Plantae.
- **Division:** Magnoliophyta.
- **Class:** Magnoliopsida.
- **Order:** Sapindales.
- **Family:** Meliaceae.
- **Genus:** *Azadirachta*.
- **Species:** *indica*.

NEEM LEAF DESCRIPTIONS

The size of the leaf: leaflets 3-6cm long on long slender petioles. Leaflets 7-17cm. The opposite is very shortly stalked 1-1.5cm long. Apex: Ovate-

lancolate, attenuate: Base- Unequal: Smooth and dark green in Colour: Bitter in taste: Odour in Typical

commercial purposes due to available of different types of chemicals. The below table shows chemical constituents list.

- **Chemical Constituents:** Different Neem plant parts are used for many disease treatment and

Sr. No.	Name of Plant Parts	Chemical Constituents Name
01	Leaf	Quercetin, Nimbosterol, Nimbin.
02	Flowers	Nimbosterol, Kaempferol, Melicitrin.
03	Bark	Nimbin, Nimbidin, Nombosterol, Margosine.
04	Seed	Azadirachtin, Azadiradione, Nimbin, Vepinin, Vilasinin, Fraxinellone.

- **Uses:**
 - ✓ Prevents development of blemishes and pimples
 - ✓ To treat acne
 - ✓ To treat bad breath
 - ✓ Prevention of diabetes
 - ✓ For treat malaria symptoms
 - ✓ For hair maintains like remove dandruff and strengthen hair.
- ✓ Prevention of teeth and gums from infection.
- ✓ Reduce risk of cancer and cardiovascular diseases
- ✓ Increase immune system.
- ✓ Neem have many more therapeutic functions.

EXCIPIENTS USED IN THE FORMULATION (28, 29, 30, 31, 32, 33, 34, 35)

Sr.No	Excipients	Description	Benefits
1.	Carbapol 940	A white, free-flowing, odourless powder with a high molecular weight and a slight acidic character.	Emulsifying, stabilizing, suspending and thickening agent
2.	Methyl Cellulose	A hydrophilic white powder in pure form and dissolves in cold water forming a clear viscous solution or a gel.	Emulsifying, stabilizing, gelling, lubricant for eye treatment, bulk laxative and thickening agent, etc.
3.	Glycerin	Soluble, nearly colorless, odourless, clear, viscous, hydrophilic liquid with a very high boiling point.	Moisturizer, Solvent, humectants & lubricant.
4.	Chloroform	A clear, colorless, volatile, non-flammable liquid with a pleasant odour.	Preservative, Perfuming, flavouring agent, etc.
5.	Sodium hydrogen carbonate	White, odourless, fine crystalline powder with neutralization properties.	pH adjuster, buffering & adhesive agent.
6.	Vanillin	It appears as white or very slightly yellow needles or crystalline solid.	Fragrance, Treats Digestive Disorders, Treatment of Acne, Treats Anxiety and Depression, anti-aging benefits, Etc.
7.	Water	A transparent, tasteless, odourless and nearly colorless liquid.	Solvent, vehicle, conditioning & cleansing agent.

SR. NO.	MATERIALS	FUNCTION
1.	Neem fresh leaves, Neem powder	Active pharmaceutical ingredient
2.	Carbapol	Gelling Agent
3.	Methyl cellulose	Polymer
4.	Glycerin	Drug Solubilizer

5.	Choloroform	Preservatives
6.	Sodium hydrogen carbonate	Buffering agent
7.	Vanillin	Flavouring Agent
8.	Distilled Water	Vehicle

1. PRELIMINARY WORK(25, 26, 27)

- **Collection of Plant material:** The leaves of neem were collected in the month of July from the campus of A.G.M. College of Pharmacy, Varur, Hubli region Karnataka, India.
- **Drying and Size Reduction of Plant Material:** The collected neem leaves were dried under shade, until leaves were dried (7-14 days). Then dried leaves were crushed into coarse powder. The coarse powder of leaves was passed through sieve No. 18 to maintain uniformity. Stored in airtight container.

2. Preparation of Extract:

- **Preparation of Dried Leaves Extract:** Already powdered neem leaves were collected. 25g of powder leaves taken in 250ml conical flask. Then add 100 ml of 95% ethanol and cover the flask with aluminium foil. Keep the container for 3 to 7 days for Maceration process by shaking occasionally.

The mixture was mixed with a sterile glass rod after 7 days. Then mixture was filtered. The solvent was removed at a temperature of less than 50 °C by heating on water bath. After solvent evaporation the residue is remain. The residue is collected and stored in airtight container.

- **Preparation of Fresh Leaves Extract:** The fresh leaves of Neem were obtain and clean with distilled water. It was then crushed in mortar and pestle. Then add 100 ml of 95% ethanol and cover the flask with aluminium foil. Keep the container for 3 to 7 days for Maceration process by shaking occasionally. The mixture was mixed with a sterile glass rod after 7 days. Then mixture was filtered. The solvent was removed at a temperature of less than 50 °C by heating on water bath. After solvent evaporation the residue is remain. The residue was collected and stored in airtight container.

▪ Composition of gel formulation

INGREDIENTS	F1	F2	F3	F4
Fresh leaves extract(gm)	1.5	----	1.5	----
Dried leaves extract(gm)	----	1.5	----	1.5
Carbopol 940(g/ml)	0.1	0.1	----	----
Methyl cellulose	----	----	0.1	0.1
Glycerin(ml)	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0
Choloroform	Q.S.	Q.S.	Q.S.	Q.S.
Sodium bicarbonate(mg)	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0
Vanillin	Q.S	Q.S	Q.S	Q.S
Distilled water	Q.S	Q.S	Q.S	Q.S

Neem gel preparation method.

CARBAPOL 940 POLYMER BASED PREPARATION (54, 55)

Carbapol 940 should be dispersed in purified water & the beaker should be kept aside for a day to swell the carbapol 940 to form gel (A).

Sufficient amount of extract (dry/fresh) taken in the beaker containing sodium bicarbonate with 10ml of distilled water.

Then B solution should be mixed & added to the beaker containing mixture with continuous stirring

↓

Now add drop wise glycerin, chloroform & pinch of vanillin.

↓

The above mixture stirred continuously to obtain the gel at required consistency.

METHYL CELLULOSE POLYMER BASED PREPARATION

Methyl cellulose should be dispersed in purified water & the beaker should be kept aside for day to swell the methyl cellulose to form gel (C).

↓

Sufficient amount of extract (dry/fresh) taken in the beaker containing sodium bicarbonate with 10ml of distilled water (D).

↓

Then D solution should be mixed & added to the beaker containing C mixture with continuous stirring.

↓

Now add drop wise glycerin, chloroform & pinch of vanillin.

↓

The above mixture stirred continuously to provide the gel at proper consistency.

❖ EVALUATION PARAMETERS:

Evaluations for the prepared formulations were carried out under major headings.

1. Phytochemicals screening of Ethonolic extract of *Azadirachta indica* leaves (36, 37, 38)

Alkaloids Test:

➤ **Mayer's test:** Take 2 ml of botanicals extract in a test tube, to that test tube add 2-3 drops of Mayer's reagent. The green colour precipitate from that indicated presence of alkaloids.

➤ **Wagner's test:** Take 2ml Wagner's reagent in test tube and add few drops of extract to the test tube. The brick colour is formed and that indicates alkaloids presence.

Flavonoids Test:

➤ **Alkaline reagent test:** To 2 ml neem extract add 2ml 2%w/v of sodium hydroxide in test tube. An intense yellow colour formed. To test tube add few drops of dilute hydrochloric acid, then colour solution converts into colourless, which indicated the presence of flavonoids.

➤ **Shinoda Test:** To 2 ml of extract add 5 drops of Hydrochloric acid and 0.5gm of magnesium pieces was added on it. It shows pink colour, the pink colour indicates flavonoids present.

Saponins Test:

➤ **Foam test:** The extract solution is taken in test tube and add water to dilute to the above solution. There was a suspension formed. Foam layer formation indicated the presence of saponins.

Terpenoids Test:

➤ Dissolve crude extract in 2ml chloroform and then evaporated for dryness. To this dried preparation add 2ml of concentrated sulphuric acid. Solution form reddish-brown colour at the interface indicates the available of terpenoids.

Glycosides Test:

➤ **Salkowaski's test:** Dissolve crude extract in 2ml chloroform. Then carefully add 2ml of concentrated sulphuric acid. After gently shake the mixture. Mixture form reddish-brown colour indicates the presence of

steroidal ring (glycine) portion of the glycoside.

- **Keller-Kilani test:** Mix 2ml crude extract with 2ml glacial acetic acid containing 1-2 drops of 2% solution of Ferric chloride in a test tube. The above mixture was added into one more test tube in which already 2 ml of concentrated sulphuric acid present. A brown ring is formed at the interface indicates the presence of cardiac glycosides.

Polyphenols and Tannins Test:

- Add 2ml of 2% ferric chloride to crude extract. A blue green or blue-black colour is formed and that indicates the presence of polyphenols and tannins.

Steroids Test:

- Add 2ml of chloroform in crude extract and then add concentrated sulphuric acid sidewall of test tube. A red colour produced in the lower chloroform layer indicates the presence of steroids.
- Add 2ml of chloroform in crude extract and then add concentrated sulphuric acid and acetic acid to the test tube. A greenish colour produced in the lower chloroform layer indicates the presence of steroids.

Coumarins Test:

- The Extract solution is concentrated to produce a residue. The obtain residue is dissolve in hot water. Then cool the solution and after words divide solution into parts.

The first part of solution was taken in test tube and add 10% w/v Ammonium Hydroxide. Another test tube was used as control. In first solution fluorescence colour produce and that was indicates the presence of coumarins.

1. Physical appearance (39, 40)

The gel formulations were evaluated for their physical parameters like colour, odour, consistency, transparency and homogeneity.

2. Determination of pH (45, 46)

The pH of the gels was detected with a digital pH meter which was calibrated before with buffer solutions of pH 4, 7 and 9. An amount of 0.5 g of gel was dissolved in 50 ml of distilled water and stored for two hours. Each formulation's pH was measured in triplicate and the average values were taken.

3. Skin Irritation Test(41, 42)

When prepared gel is applied on skin to check any irritation happens. It found that all four formulations are safe because no skin irritation happens.

4. Determination of Viscosity (47, 48)

Viscosity of each formulation was determined using Rotational viscometer with spindle number 4 at room temperature at specific rpm.

5. Determination of Washability (49, 50)

The small quantity of gel is applied on hand and then wash the hand by using tap water. All formulation were wash easily

6. Determination of Spreadability (51)

The spreadability prepare gel was calculated by two glass slide method. The required quantity of prepared neem gel is placed on lower slide and above that one more slide is kept in such way that gel is sandwiched between two slide and air is present between slides is removed by pressing slides. The extra gel adhere to the slide is removed. Afterwards the setup is kept on stand and lower slide is firmly held by clips at opposite side of fangs. To upper slide weighing pan is connected and 20gm of weight is placed. Then time taken by upper slide completely detach from lower slide is noted and the spreadability was calculated by using the following formula:

$$S = m \cdot \frac{l}{t}$$

S= Spreadability, m= the weight tied to the upper slides (gm), l= the length of glass slide (cm), t= the time taken (sec)

7. Drug content(43, 44)

Take 100ml of volumetric flask and add 0.2 gm of the gel formulation or gel which equivalent to 10mg of drug. To flask add 20 ml of phosphate buffer pH 7.4 and mixed 15 minutes. Then make up the volume to 100 ml. Take 1ml solution from above flask and add 10 ml phosphate buffer solution of pH 7.4 for further dilution. Then take absorbance value at 330 nm by using UV spectroscopy and note down reading.

8. Diffusion Studies (52, 53)

The measuring cylinder was taken and bottom end of measuring cylinder is broken. Now both the end measuring cylinder are open. To bottom end onion membrane is covered by using glue or thread. This act as inner compartment. To inner compartment add 10ml of 0.1N Hydrochloric Acid. Then inner compartment is inserted into 100ml 0.1N Hydrochloric Acid containing beaker, which is act as outer compartment. Add magnetic bead to outer compartment to stirr the contents and set up is kept magnetic stirrer and maintain 37°C. The required

quantity of gel was added to inner compartment add start the magnetic stirrer. At every 5mins interval (5, 10, 15, 20, 25, 30mins) the samples were withdrawn and same quantity of fresh solution were added to maintain sink condition. The withdrawn samples absorbance were estimated at 330nm.

RESULTS

Morphological Characterization of *Azadirachta indica* leaves:

Leaves of *Azadirachta indica* were green in color, bitter in taste, Length – 1.5-3cm, Width 1- 1.5cm in size, ovate in shape and Rough outer periphery.

Phytochemical Analysis of *Azadirachta Indica* Extract:

The phytochemical study revealed the presence of various phytochemicals in the ethanolic extracts. The results were mention in Table.

Sr. No.	Tests	Outcome
1.	Alkaloids test	+ ve
2.	Flavonoids test	+ ve
3.	Saponins test	+ve
4.	Terpenoids test	+ve
5.	Glycosides test	- ve
6.	Polyphenols and tannins test	+ve
7.	Steroids test	+ve
8.	Coumarins test	-ve

❖ Physical appearance:

The prepared formulations were evaluated for the Colour, Odour and Consistency. The Colour of the gel was observed by visual examination. The Odour of gel was found to be pleasant. The State of gel was examined visually. The gel was semisolid in nature. The formulation was examined by rubbing gel on hand manually. These Formulations having a smooth consistency.

❖ Determination of pH

The pH values of all prepared formulation ranged from 4.66-5.91 which are considered acceptable to avoid the risk of irritation upon application to the skin because adult skin pH is 5.5. All the formulations had very slightly alkaline pH which was compatible with normal skin physiology. The results were shown in the Table.

Table: pH Values:

Formulations	Reading 1	Reading 2	Reading 3	Mean±SD
NCF	6.1	5.5	5.7	5.7± 0.90
NCD	5.0	5.1	5.3	5.1± 0.59
NMF	6.2	62.1	5.8	6.0 ±0.65
NMD	5.9	6.1	6.1	6.0± 0.64

Determination of viscosity:

Viscosity is measure of the thickness of a fluid. Results were shown in Table.

Table: Viscosity Values:

Formulations	Reading 1	Reading 2	Reading 3	Mean±SD
NCF	4418	4400	4415	4409±13
NCD	2438	2445	2432	2438±8
NMF	925	910	915	917±24
NMD	780	810	800	797±26

❖ **Determination of Spreadability:**

better the spreadability. Therefore according to statement F2C had better spreadability

Spreadability is carried out for all four formulations. The less time take for the separation of both the slide

Table: Spreadability values:

Formulation	Reading 1	Reading 2	Reading 3	Mean±SD
NCF	4.1	4.0	4.0	4.0±0.4
NCD	3.5	3.8	3.7	3.6 ±0.7
NMF	5.5	5.4	5.8	5.6 ±0.6
NMF	6.3	5.5	5.8	5.8 ±0.6

❖ **Drug content:**

Table: Drug content values:

Formulation	Reading 1	Reading 2	Reading 3	Mean \pm SD
NCF	98	99	99	99 \pm 8.12
NCD	99	98	96	98 \pm 8
NMF	95	97	98	97 \pm 7.93
NMD	97	97	98	97 \pm 8.06

❖ **Skin Irritation test:**

All the gel formulations were found to be safe while being applied on the skin and there was no irritation or sensitivity to the skin.

Washability test was carried out by applying a small amount of gel on the hand and then washing it with help of tap water. It observed that all the four formulations were easily washable.

❖ **Determination of Washability:**

❖ **Diffusion studies: Observation table for amount of drug release**

Formulations	Amount of Drug Release							Slope	Intercept
	0min	5min	10min	15min	20min	25min	30 min		
NCF	0.00	5.062	8.522	13.55	19.21	26.76	30.22	5.16	5.91

NCD	0.00	4.252	10.01	14.19	20.62	26.09	29.30	5.07	5.38
NMF	0.00	5.301	9.102	14.65	21.38	25.18	29.27	4.99	4.99
NMD	0.00	5.36	9.46	13.56	20.18	25.55	30.28	5.06	5.36

DIFFUSION STUDIES GRAPH OF NCF

DIFFUSION STUDIES GRAPH OF NMF

DIFFUSION STUDIES GRAPH OF NCD

DIFFUSION STUDIES GRAPH OF NMD

In graph: time: 1- 0min, 2- 05min, 3- 10min, 4- 15min, 5- 20min, 6- 25min, 7-30min.

Summary and Conclusion

- In this study we prepare the Neem face gel by using different polymers like Carbopol and Methylcellulose. The prepared Neem face gel is evaluated for various parameters.
- The Neem extract collected from using Neem leaves by drying under shade in laboratory. They were pulverized to make coarse powder. The coarse powder of leaves were passed through sieve No. 18 to maintain uniformity and stored in airtight jars, kept in cool and dry place for study.

➤ The purity of neem gel is confirmed by evaluating phytoconstituents of extracted neem gel and we found different phytoconstituents are presents and compare the results with standard results. The results confirm the extracted neem gel is pure.

➤ The face gel of neem and polymers was prepared by using different materials as mentioned in formulation table and method as explain in methodology

➤ The prepared neem gel was evaluated for various parameters as mentioned in aim and objectives. The results are as follows in the table

Results of all evaluation parameters

Parameters	Formulations			
	NCF	NCD	NMF	NMD
pH value	5.7 ± 0.90	5.1 ± 0.59	6.00 ± 0.65	6.00 ± 0.64
Spreadability [gm.cm/sec]	4.0 ± 0.4	3.6 ± 0.7	5.6 ± 0.6	5.8 ± 0.6
Viscosity [cpa]	4409 ± 13	2438 ± 8	917 ± 24	797 ± 26
Drug Content [%]	99 ± 8.12	98 ± 8	97 ± 7.93	97 ± 8.06
Diffusion [%]	30.22	29.30	29.27	30.28
Washability	Satisfied	Satisfied	Satisfied	Satisfied
Skin Irritation Test	Satisfied	Satisfied	Satisfied	Satisfied

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